

Kinetics of Substitution of Aquo-ligands from *cis*-Diaquo-bis-oxalatochromate(III) Ion by Picolinic Acid in Water – Ethanol Mixture

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The kinetic behaviour of *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ with picolinic acid as a function of temperature, pH and picolinic acid concentration has been studied spectrophotometrically at pH 6.0. The following rate law has been established,

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 [\text{Complex}][\text{Pic}^-]$$

where, k_2 is the second order rate constant. The rate is slow at low pH around 4, increases with increase of pH and reaches maximum at pH 6.3. The rate is almost constant at pH 6.0 – 6.3 and decreases with increase of pH. Values of activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have been evaluated and a reaction mechanism involving S_N2 path has been suggested.

ANATION reactions of various chromium(III) aquo-complexes were studied extensively by various workers. Some authors¹⁻⁴ observed that the reaction rates are independent of the concentration of entering anions and proposed S_N1 mechanism, others⁵⁻¹¹ interpreted their results implying that bond-making plays a significant role in anation reactions as evidenced by the small but definite dependence of the formation rates on the nature and concentration of ligands. A few of them^{9,10} also showed that substitution proceeds through the formation of ion-pair association. Thus, the ligand substitution reactions in case of Cr^{III} complexes do not follow any single mechanism, and the reaction path depends on the nature of the incoming ligand and the experimental conditions. This prompted us to study the kinetics of substitution of aquo-ligands from *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ by a series of pyridine carboxylic acids in water – ethanol mixture. The present study relates to anation of *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ by picolinate ion.

Experimental

cis-K[Cr(C₂O₄)₂(H₂O)₂].2H₂O [Complex-I] was prepared following the reported method¹², and its purity was checked by analysis. The prepared complex showed maximum absorbance at 416 nm and 562 nm being concordant with the literature¹³, ϵ values at the two wavelength were experimentally determined and found to be 67.25 (lit. 68.5) and 50.0 (lit. 51.0) respectively. Chromium and oxalate found experimentally were 14.84% (calcd. 15.34) and 50.9% (calcd. 51.90), respectively. Solutions of picolinic acid and the complex of desired concentration were prepared by dissolving the calculated amounts in 30% ethanol. The pH values of the

reaction mixtures were adjusted with perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. A Elico LI10T pH meter was used for measurement of pH and a Beckman D.B.G. spectrophotometer for absorbance measurements.

Due to high solubility it was not possible to isolate the product (Complex-II) of the reaction between *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ and picolinic acid in pure crystalline form. However, the formation of the product in solution was indicated by following absorbance of the reaction mixtures, thermostated at 65° for 24 h, containing the complex and ligand in ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 5. Their solutions showed absorption maxima at 410 ($\epsilon=92.7$) and 540 nm ($\epsilon=72.6$). Shifting of λ_{max} (from that of Complex-I) towards lower wavelengths and higher value of extinction coefficient indicate the formation of a heterochelate by picolinic acid in solution. Composition of the product (1 : 1) in solution was confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation.

The temperature for any set of experiments were thermostatically controlled ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The rate of reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at 520 nm where the molar extinction coefficient of the product and the reacting complex differ appreciably. The reaction medium was 30% aqueous ethanol.

Procedure for kinetic study : Equal volumes of solutions of picolinic acid and the complex of desired concentration were taken in reaction vessel after adjusting pH by dropwise addition of HClO₄ or NaOH solution, and kept at the desired temperature for appropriate time. The composition of the experimental solution was such that the first order rate law was applicable, and pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) for each experiment was evaluated

graphically by plotting $\log (D_{\infty} - D_0 / D_{\infty} - D_t)$ vs time, D_0 , D_t and D_{∞} being the optical density values initially, after time t and after completing of the reaction, respectively. The pseudo-first order plots were linear (Fig. 1). However, the rate constants were calculated on the basis of the least-square method and were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Fig. 1. Graphical presentation of k_{obs} (60.2°) $\mu=0.30 M$ $[Cr(C_2O_4)_2(H_2O)_2]^- = 0.01 M$, pH=6; $[Pic^-]$, (A) 0.1, (B) 0.15, (C) 0.2, (D) 0.25 and (E) 0.3 M.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variation of complex concentration on rate constant: In this set of experiment, the concentration of Complex-I was varied in the range 0.005–0.015 M at a constant excess concentration 0.15 M of picolinic acid. Ionic strength (0.16 M), pH (6) and temperature (60.2°) were also kept constant. At pH 6, $cis-[Cr(Ox)_2(H_2O)_2]^-$ and Pic^- are the reacting species. It was observed that the rate of reaction is first order with respect to [Complex-I], i.e. $\frac{d}{dt} [Complex-II] = k_{obs} [Complex-I]$.

Effect of varying picolinic acid concentration on the rate constant: In these experiments, the complex concentration was kept constant at 0.01 M and picolinic acid concentration was varied over the range 0.1–0.30 M at 50.3, 55.0, 60.2 and 64.5°. pH was kept constant at 6 and the ionic strength kept at 0.30 M. The effect of ligand concentration on the rate constant is shown in Table 1. Fig. 1 shows the plot of $\log (D_{\infty} - D_0 / D_{\infty} - D_t)$ against time at 60.2°.

At constant pH 6.0 the rate constant increases with increase in $[Pic^{-1}]$ at each temperature (Table 1) according to the rate law

$$Rate = k_2 [Complex-I][Pic^{-1}] = k_{obs} [Complex-I]$$

[Complex-I] = 0.01 M, [Pic ⁻¹] M	Ionic strength = 0.30 M, pH = 6.0			
	$k_{obs} (\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$			
	50.3°	55.0°	60.2°	64.5°
0.10	1.7	2.5	5.0	6.0
0.15	2.5	3.7	7.0	9.3
0.20	3.5	5.2	9.0	11.8
0.25	4.2	6.3	11.6	14.7
0.30	5.0	7.4	13.9	17.7

where, k_2 is the second order rate constant and k_{obs} is the pseudo-first order rate constant. From the slope of the linear plot k_{obs} vs $[Pic^{-1}]$, the value of k_2 can be calculated. These plots of k_{obs} vs $[Pic^{-1}]$ at four different temperatures 50.3, 55.0, 60.2 and 64.5° are shown in Fig. 2 and values of k_2 are shown in Table 2. The linear dependence of rate on $[Pic^{-1}]$ suggests that the reaction proceeds through associative path.

Fig. 2. Dependence of k_{obs} on picolinic acid concn., $[Cr(C_2O_4)_2(H_2O)_2]^- = 0.01 M$, pH=6, at (A) 50.3°, (B) 55°, (C) 60.2° and (D) 64.5°.

Temp. (°C)	50.3	55.0	60.2	64.5
$k_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1})$	17.06	25.2	46.59	59.06

Effect of variation of pH on rate constant : In this set of experiments, the concentration of the complex and picolinic acid were kept constant at 0.01 and 0.1 *M*, respectively, and pH was varied from 4.0 to 7.95. The pH dependence of rate constants (Table 3) indicates that the rate constant values pass through a maximum around pH 6.3. To explain the effect of pH variation on the rate constant, the equilibria (1) and (2) for picolinic acid and equilibria (3), (4) for *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ should be considered.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF pH ON THE RATE CONSTANT

[PicH] = 0.1 *M*, [Complex] = 0.01 *M*, Ionic strength = 0.11 *M*, Temp. = 60.2°

pH	$k_{obs} \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	pH	$k_{obs} \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹
4.0	1.60	6.0	5.00
5.0	2.26	6.3	5.92
5.45	3.93	6.95	4.41
5.8	4.55	7.95	4.07

At lower pH values, where the complex remains in diaquo form, the reaction is slow due to the protonation of carboxylate ion of the ligand. At pH 6.0 and above, picolinic acid exists mainly as its anionic form. It is clear that lower the pH, higher is the protonation of picolinate anion; automatically the donor capability of the ligand decreases and as a result the pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) decreases.

The experimental results also show that at pH 6.0–6.3, k_{obs} remains almost constant and again it decreases with increase of pH. In the pH range 6.0–6.3, picolinic acid remains mainly in its anionic

form Pic⁻, and the substrate complex mainly in diaquo form. But as pH increases above 6.3, the substrate complex is converted into hydroxo complex. The hydroxide ion in hydroxo complex exerts an electromeric effect which increases electron density on chromium and reduces the possibility of nucleophilic attack by picolinate ion on reaction site. So rate constants should decrease with increase in pH above 6.3. Thus, in the pH range 4.0–7.95, the pseudo-first order rate constant of the reaction increases at first, with the increase of pH reaches a maximum around 6.3 and then decreases.

Effect of ionic strength on the rate constant : In this set of experiments performed at pH 6.0 and 60.2°, the concentrations of Complex-I and picolinic acid were kept constant at 0.01 and 0.10 *M*, respectively, and ionic strength was varied by the addition of desired amount of NaClO₄ in the reaction mixture. The rate constant values indicate that the reaction is insensitive to ionic strength.

Effect of temperature on rate constant : The activation parameters have been calculated from the plot of log k_2 vs $1/T$. The values are found to be $\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 70.3 \pm 1.5$ kJ mol⁻¹, and $\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -76.7 \pm 3.0$ Jk⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

Mechanism : The above results suggest that under the experimental conditions employed the reaction proceeds through the following mechanism, S_N2 path :

The above mechanism is supported by comparison of activation parameters of picolinic acid substitution with other ligand on *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ (Table 4).

It appears from Table 4 that activation enthalpy ΔH_2^\ddagger of picolinic acid substitution is lower than that of isotopic water exchange¹¹ and dipyriddy⁶ and *o*-phenanthroline substitution in *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻. This indicates that the nucleophilic

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF ANALOGOUS SYSTEMS

System	ΔH_2^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH_2^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS_2^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔS_2^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
<i>cis</i> -[Cr(Ox) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ⁻ + Picolinic acid ^a	70.3 ± 1.5	—	-76.7 ± 3.0	—
<i>cis</i> -[Cr(Ox) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ⁻ + Dipyriddy ^{1b}	82.9	48.1	-42.7	-195.5
<i>cis</i> -[Cr(Ox) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ⁻ + <i>o</i> -Phenanthroline ^b	87.1	48.1	-20.9	-195.5
<i>cis</i> -[Cr(Ox) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ⁻ + H ₂ O (isotopic water exchange) ^c	75.4	—	-90.4	—

^a This work. ^b Ref. 6. ^c Ref. 16.

attack is more favourable in case of picolinate anion. This is logical since α, α' -dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline are rigid molecules whereas picolinic acid is flexible and can easily form a bond in activated state.

Associative mechanism for the picolinic acid substitution is further supported by the effect of pH on the reaction rate. At lower pH values, where the complex remains in diaquo form, the reaction is slow due to protonation of carboxylate ion of the ligand. The rate increases with the increase of pH from 4 to 6 due to increased donor capability of picolinate anion. Above pH 6.3, the rate constant again decreases with the increase of pH. This is due to the formation of hydroxo aquo species. The hydroxide ion in hydroxo aquo complex forms π -bond and increases the electron density on chromium centre which reduces the possibility of nucleophilic attack by picolinate ion on reaction site; thus the rate decreases.

Thus we can conclude that aquo ligand substitution in *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ by picolinate anion involves the formation of new metal-ligand bond in transition state and the mechanism is associative in nature.

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